

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D1.8 REPORT ON KEY COMMUNICATION EVENTS - 2ND REPORTING PERIOD

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1. INTRODUCTION

Dissemination and Communication (D&C) activities have been crucial from the start of the project, helping to maximize its impact by reaching a broad audience and facilitating the uptake of results. This Deliverable D1.8 - "*Report on Key Communication Events - 2nd Reporting Period*," outlines the strategies and results of the communication activities during the project's second reporting period (M13–M30, 1/5/2023–31/10/2024). Building on the roadmap in Deliverable D1.4 - "*Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan*," which defines target audiences, tools, and events for effective dissemination, these activities are regularly updated to stay aligned with ongoing developments. Specifically, progress on D&C activities, first reported in D1.5 - "*Annual Report on Key Communication Events*," is updated in this deliverable (D1.8) and will continue to be tracked in the final report at M48 (D1.12 - "*Reports on Key Communication Events - 3rd Reporting Period*") alongside D1.16 - "*Updated Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan*."

Summaries of the Consortium's communication actions are presented in tables within this report. All partners contribute to raising awareness and transferring results to public, scientific, technical, and industrial audiences, ensuring that all fields involved in the project—biology, soft robotics, chemistry, smart hydrogels, and mathematical modelling—are well represented. The active contributions from all partners have been essential in maintaining a comprehensive and up-to-date database of project outputs across all relevant disciplines.

1.1 MAPWORMS DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

The MAPWORMS dissemination and communication efforts are focused on sharing the project's research across Europe and internationally. The Consortium strongly believes in the importance of inspiring future generations to engage in research and entrepreneurship. One of MAPWORMS' key goals is to demonstrate to young people how careers in science and engineering can have a significant and positive impact on society. This has been actively pursued through participation in various outreach initiatives, such as science fairs, educational workshops, and interactive sessions with students. These events have provided a platform to showcase how scientific innovations can address real-world challenges, encouraging youth to consider paths in STEM fields. Additionally, MAPWORMS has been actively involved in numerous high-profile events for experts within the scientific and industrial communities, including international conferences, industrial forums, and specialized workshops. These events have facilitated deeper engagement with academic peers, industry leaders, and potential collaborators, furthering the project's visibility and fostering knowledge exchange.

At the outset of the project, specific D&C channels were established, all leveraging various digital tools. In today's landscape, digital tools are essential for effectively connecting an initiative with its target audience. MAPWORMS has dedicated significant effort to

enhancing its digital presence, particularly through its website and social media platforms, not only to showcase project outcomes but also to build a community with a keen interest in the multidisciplinary approach including all branches of the project.

To ensure consistent planning, monitoring, and enhancement of these D&C activities, the MAPWORMS Consortium holds monthly online meetings (Figure 1). Over the course of the project, 26 such meetings were conducted, serving not only as a forum for collaboration but also for ongoing evaluation of progress in outreach efforts.

Figure 1. MAPWORMS monthly meeting on 10th January 2024.

In the following sections, we provide a detailed analysis of the performance of our social media channels and website, highlighting engagement metrics and audience growth. Additionally, we offer a comprehensive overview of our participation in various events aimed at the general public, as well as our involvement in conferences and forums within the scientific and industrial communities. A full report on the publications produced by the Consortium is also included, showcasing our efforts to disseminate research findings through academic journals and other relevant platforms.

2. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

2.1 PROJECT WEBSITE

The project's website, www.mapworms.eu, was launched in July 2022 and has since served as the central platform for engaging with diverse audiences. This website functions as a key point of interaction, offering comprehensive updates on the project's objectives, achievements, and the latest dissemination materials. It is designed to provide easy access to a variety of resources, including project outcomes, research findings, and upcoming events.

To maximize visibility and reach, Search Engine Optimization (SEO) strategies were integrated into the website, ensuring that it ranks well in search engine results and attracts organic traffic. These efforts aim to make it easier for users to discover the site through relevant keywords related to MAPWORMS' key areas, such as robotics, smart materials, and marine biology. The effectiveness of these strategies is continuously monitored using WP Statistics – WordPress tool, which provides detailed insights into user behaviour and site performance, helping the team optimize content and engagement over time.

NUMBER OF VISITS AND VISITORS

In the first 30 months of the project, the MAPWORMS website attracted a total of 7,028 unique visitors (unique individuals that visited the website). The highest spike in user activity occurred in January 2024, which coincided with the 21st month of the project's timeline, indicating increased interest and engagement during this period. Over the same 30-month span, the site recorded 17,185 total visits, reflecting users returning to the platform multiple times to access updated content and project information. Figure 2 provides a visual representation of both the number of unique visitors and the total visits over this timeframe, showcasing the website's growth in traffic. The audience for the MAPWORMS website is quite diverse, with visitors coming from various parts of the world. The United States, Italy, and the United Kingdom stand out as the top three countries generating the most traffic, indicating strong international interest in the project's work. A detailed breakdown of the visitor distribution across the top 15 countries is illustrated in Figure 3, further highlighting the global reach of the MAPWORMS digital presence.

Figure 2. MAPWORMS website visitors and visits (Source: WP Statistics – WordPress).

Rank	Flag	Country	Visitor Count
1		United States	2,448
2		Italy	633
3		United Kingdom	463
4		Singapore	375
5		Germany	348
6		India	203
7		France	176
8		Russian Federation	176
9		Canada	154
10		Netherlands	146
11		Sweden	144
12		Ireland	129
13		Australia	116
14		China	112
15		Greece	105

Figure 3. Visitors' Demographics distribution (Source: WP Statistics – WordPress).

These insights into visitor demographics and site engagement are key for optimizing communication strategies, ensuring that the project continues to effectively reach and engage with both scientific communities and the broader public across multiple regions.

PAGE VIEWS

During the first 30 months of the project, the two most visited pages on the MAPWORMS website were the "Contact" page, and the "Project" page. These pages clearly reflect the core interests of the website's visitors, with many users seeking more information on the project itself, the organizations involved, and how to get in touch with the Consortium. This indicates that the audience is not only engaging with the project's content but is also actively interested in establishing connections or learning more about the Consortium partners.

The top 10 most-visited pages, as illustrated in Figure 4, offer further insights into user behaviour, highlighting a consistent interest in various sections of the website, including the news and posts that are regularly published on the site. These data help the team better understand which areas of the website are most effective in capturing user attention and informs future content development and enhancements aimed at maximizing user engagement.

▲ Top Pages

ID	Title	Link	Visits
1	Contact	/contact/	2,769
2	Project	/project-1/	978
3	Vexlum	/vexlum/	828
4	information data protection	/information-data-protection	807
5	SSSA	/sssa/	632
6	Results	/results/	577
7	News & Events	/news-events/	523
8	HUJI	/huji/	503
9	ACMIT	/acmit/	485
10	MAPWORMS Project shines at the INNODAYS Innovation Exhibition hosted by the Region of Crete	/2023/12/07/mapworms-innoday-innovation-exhibition-region-of-crete/	471

Figure 4. MAPWORMS page views (Source: WP Statistics – WordPress).

Understanding which pages attract the most traffic is essential for refining the overall website strategy, ensuring that key information is easily accessible, and that users' needs are consistently met. This ongoing analysis allows the MAPWORMS team to continuously improve the website's performance and user experience, driving higher engagement and ensuring the project's visibility remains strong.

2.2 SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS

MAPWORMS profiles on key social media platforms, including [Facebook®](#) and [LinkedIn](#), were created in the early months of the project and have been continuously updated to reflect ongoing developments. At the beginning of the project, a Twitter page was created, but due to low interest on this platform, the focus shifted to LinkedIn and Facebook for better engagement. Indeed, the selection of these channels followed a careful analysis of each platform's potential to support the communication goals of the project. It became clear that not all platforms were equally suited to achieving our objectives. We chose to focus on LinkedIn and Facebook, where active scientific and professional communities align with the topics covered by MAPWORMS.

These platforms offered opportunities to:

1. Engage a targeted audience with interest in science and technology.
2. Foster conversations that could extend beyond the scientific community and reach the general public.
3. Attract more people to MAPWORMS and increase interest in the broader field of scientific research.

To achieve these aims, we adopted an approachable and friendly tone to convey complex scientific concepts in a simpler, more effective way.

The management of these social media channels falls under the responsibility of WP1 - *Project Coordination, Dissemination, and Communication*, led by SSSA. Partners actively participate by using both their personal and organization accounts (LinkedIn, Facebook) to share updates and contributions. From the project's outset, a weekly posting calendar was established and shared within the Consortium. This calendar rotates responsibility among partners, ensuring a new post or update is published each week. The rotation of contributions adds variety and maintains the project's multidisciplinary focus across social channels.

Social media performance is monitored using the built-in analytics tools provided by each platform, and these metrics are regularly reviewed to assess the reach and engagement of our communications.

LINKEDIN

During the first 30 months of the project, the MAPWORMS LinkedIn account saw steady growth, attracting 659 followers. Content was shared regularly, with an average of one post per week, resulting in a total of 40 posts in the past 365 days. These posts provided updates on project milestones, technological advancements, and general progress, helping to engage and inform the scientific and professional communities.

Two posts, in particular, stood out for their high levels of engagement. The most popular post, which focused on the presentation of our project results at the workshop titled **Bio-Inspired Medical Robotics: From Evolution to Revolution in Healthcare** at the 16th Hamlyn Symposium on Medical Robotics of the Hamlyn Centre for Robotic Surgery in London held on June 25th, 2024, achieved an impressive 2,929 organic impressions, showcasing strong interest in the project's results. The second most-viewed post, receiving 2,373 organic impressions, featured the workshop on "Fluid Driven Soft Actuators: Challenges and Opportunities." organized by MAPWORMS at the Robosoft 2024 conference in San Diego, USA, highlighting the innovative technology involved in the project.

Throughout this period, MAPWORMS maintained consistent interaction with its audience. Figure 5 illustrates the variety of reactions—likes, comments, and shares—over the past 365 days showcasing the high level of engagement from followers. These interactions reflect the interest in MAPWORMS and its cutting-edge research, helping to build a network of supporters within the professional and scientific sectors.

Figure 5. Monthly aggregate reactions to MAPWORMS LinkedIn posts over the past 365 days. Red stars indicate the dates when posts were made.

In terms of overall performance, Figure 6 (left) demonstrates how organic impressions were distributed across posts, and Figure 6 (right) presents the number of clicks. These figures show the reach of the project's communication efforts. In total, MAPWORMS LinkedIn posts garnered 557 reactions over the past 365 days.

Figure 6. Number of organics impression (left) and clicks (right) on MAPWORMS LinkedIn posts over the past 365 days.

FACEBOOK

As of the first 30 months of the project, the MAPWORMS Facebook page has garnered a growing audience of 209 followers. Engagement with content has been consistent, with a post reach of 977 in just the past 28 days. A detailed breakdown of key metrics related to the Facebook page for the past 28 days is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Key metrics related to MAPWORMS page on Facebook for the past 28 days

Post reach	977
Post engagement	99
Reactions	50
Photo views	18

On average, new content is posted on Facebook once a week, helping to maintain a steady flow of information and updates for the audience. Over the past 12 months, the project published 38 posts, covering a range of topics including project milestones, research highlights, and upcoming events.

The most successful post during the past 90 days was made on 27 September 2024, which focused on the presentation on MAPWORMS delivered by CoNISMa in the 83rd Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI) and the 57th European Marine Biology Symposium. This post generated significant engagement, receiving 722 impressions and 25 reactions, reflecting strong interest from the community in the project's activities. This level of engagement demonstrates the effectiveness of using Facebook to not only share information but to actively involve followers in the project's journey.

Through regular updates and targeted posts, the MAPWORMS Facebook page continues to serve as an important channel for building awareness and fostering interaction among a wide audience, from scientific communities to the general public.

3. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATIONS ACTIVITIES

3.1 PUBLICATIONS

The publications produced by the MAPWORMS Consortium during the first 30 months of the project are summarized in Table 2.

It is important to highlight that all project partners are actively working to align with best practices in Open Science. Whenever possible, “Gold” open access publishing is pursued, ensuring that MAPWORMS findings are widely accessible to the international scientific community without restrictions. This approach maximizes the dissemination and impact of the research produced by the Consortium.

In cases where “Gold” open access is not available, such as with certain conference proceedings or abstracts, the Consortium adopts a “Green” open access model. This allows authors to share pre-prints of their work, making them freely available to the wider community. Furthermore, all published contributions are archived in institutional or public repositories, taking advantage of the extensive resources and capabilities within the Consortium. We have a dedicated community in Zenodo (EU Open Research Repository) called “[MAPWORMS COMMUNITY](#)” to upload our pre-prints, presentations, public deliverables, etc. These efforts ensure that MAPWORMS research remains accessible and contributes to global scientific progress.

Table 1. MAPWORMS Publications M1-M30.

Author	Title	Journal/ conference	Type	Status	Date	DOI/ Link	Open Access	Comments
CoNISMa	Marine annelids as models for innovative robots	81 st Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	Poster	Presented	Sep. 2022		No	The poster was presented during the conference but not published
SSSA	A Bioinspired Fluid-Filled Soft Linear Actuator	Soft Robotics Journal	Journal	Published	Nov. 2022	DOI	Yes	
SSSA	Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS: the MAPWORMS Project	European Robotics Forum (ERF 2023)	Poster	Presented	Mar. 2023		No	The poster was presented during the ERF Forum but not published
HCMR	Scientific community needs: FAIR and credible data repositories. The case of MedOBIS Repository and MAPWORMS Project	International Ocean Data Conference - II (IODC-II)	Poster	Published	Mar. 2023	Link DOI	Yes	The conference titled “The data we need for the Ocean we want” took place at the UNESCO Headquarters in Paris
SSSA	Mechanics of tubular meshes made of helical fibers and application to modeling McKibben artificial muscles	6th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2023)	Poster	Presented	Apr. 2023	DOI	Yes	
HUJI	Stimuli-Responsive DNA-Based Hydrogels on Surfaces for Switchable Bioelectrocatalysis and Controlled Release of Loads	Applied Materials and Interfaces	Journal	Published	Jul. 2023		Yes	
CoNISMa	Towards a new standard for marine annelid checklists: the Salento Peninsula as a case study	82 nd Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	Poster	Presented	Sep. 2023	DOI	YES	

CoNISMa	Biodiversity patterns in marine annelids associated to intertidal coralline algae along the Salento Peninsula	14 th National Conference on Biodiversity/1 st International Conference on Mediterranean Biodiversity	Poster	Presented	Sep. 2023		No	The poster was presented during the conference but not published
HUJI	Stiffness-Switchable Biocatalytic pH-Responsive DNA-Functionalized Polyacrylamide Cryogels and Their Mechanical Applications	Advanced Functional Materials	Journal	Published	Oct. 2023	DOI	Yes	
HUJI	Chemical and Photochemical-Driven Dissipative Fe ³⁺ /Fe ²⁺ -Ion Cross-Linked Carboxymethyl Cellulose Gels Operating Under Aerobic Conditions: Applications for Transient Controlled Release and Mechanical Actuation	Journal of the American Chemical Society JACS	Journal	Published	Mar. 2024	DOI	Yes	
CoNISMa	Non-indigenous polychaetes along the Salento Peninsula: new records and first molecular data	Mediterranean Marine Science	Journal	Published	Apr. 2024	DOI	Yes	
HCMR	Applying Fair principles to micro-CT data, the case of MAPWORMS project	5th International Congress on Applied Ichthyology, Oceanography, and Aquatic Environment (HydroMediIT 2024)	Presenta- tion- Procee- dings	Presented- Published	May- June 2024	LINK DOI	Yes	
CoNISMa	Report of the non-indigenous <i>Myrianida pachycera</i> (Annelida: Syllidae) in the Mediterranean Sea	BiolInvasions Records	Journal	Submitted	Oct 2024		Yes	

3.2 PRESS RELEASES

The press releases issued by the MAPWORMS Consortium during the first 30 months of the project are detailed in Table 3. These press releases played a critical role in communicating key achievements to a broader audience, including the general public, stakeholders, and the scientific community. By distributing timely and well-crafted press releases, the Consortium has been able to generate visibility for the project and raise awareness about its objectives, progress, and innovative developments.

Each press release has been tailored to highlight significant breakthroughs, project events, and collaborations, helping to maintain ongoing public engagement and foster interest in MAPWORMS' research activities. These efforts are part of the Consortium's broader communication strategy, aimed at ensuring that the project's key messages reach both specialized and non-specialized audiences alike.

Table 2. MAPWORMS Press Releases M1-M30.

Author	Title	Magazine	Type	Status	Date	DOI/ Link	Open Access	Comments
SSSA	The interaction between biology and engineering develops new bio-inspired robotic solutions in the medical field and for marine monitoring. MAPWORMS, coordinated by the BioRobotics Institute, is the new project funded by European Commission	Sant'Anna Magazine	Press release	Published	May 2022	Link	Yes	

HCMR	MAPWORMS: Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in worms	Cretalive news	Press release	Published	Dec. 2022	Link	Yes	This press release is in Greek
SSSA	Una nuova generazione di robot si prende cura degli uomini (a new robot generation takes care of humans)	Class	Press release	Published	Feb. 2023	Link	No	This press release is in Italian
CoNIS Ma	Robot ispirati ai vermi marini: l'idea in un progetto di ricerca italiano	Kodami	Press release	Published	Aug. 2023	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNIS Ma	Mapworms: progetto di ricerca italiano sviluppa robot ispirati a vermi marini	Lega Nerd	Press release	Published	Aug. 2023	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNIS Ma	Mapworms, l'affascinante progetto italiano dei robot vermi	DigiTech.News	Press release	Published	Aug. 2023	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNIS Ma	Vermi robot, nuova frontiera in soccorso alla vita umana	Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno	Press release	Published	Oct. 2023	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNIS Ma	Vermi robot iniettati nel corpo per operazioni oggi impossibili: nasce il prototipo ispirato a organismi presenti nei mari pugliesi	La Repubblica	Press release	Published	Oct. 2023	Link	No	Press release in Italian
HCMR	Τα σκουλήκια εμπνέουν τους επιστήμονες, γίνονται ρομπότ και το δεξί χέρι ενός χειρουργού!	Cretalive news	Press release	Published	May 2024	Link	Yes	This press release is in Greek

3.3 EVENTS

MAPWORMS partners actively engaged in a variety of events across multiple disciplines, including robotics, biology, chemistry, smart materials, and mathematical modelling, with the goal of increasing the project's visibility and reaching diverse audiences (see Table 4). By participating in high-profile scientific conferences worldwide, the Consortium was able to disseminate research findings to experts in fields directly related to the project's scope. These events provided valuable opportunities to present cutting-edge developments and foster collaborations within the scientific community.

In addition to attending conferences, MAPWORMS partners regularly participated in public outreach activities such as open days and other science communication events, which helped bridge the gap between researchers and the general public (Figure 7). These efforts have been particularly effective in showcasing the real-world impact of the project's innovations. Furthermore, the project teams presented their research to high-school students, aiming to inspire the next generation of scientists by introducing them to cutting-edge topics in science and technology. All partners – especially the two companies, ACMIT and VEXLUM – have been active in presenting the project to industrial networks. For instance, ACMIT has shared the project with their existing and potential partners (approximately 60 companies worldwide), reaching around 100 people per year through these efforts.

To support these dissemination activities, various forms of informative materials were developed, including leaflets, videos, and gadgets. From the early stages of the project, MAPWORMS leaflets were created and distributed at conferences, workshops, and other events. These leaflets provided a comprehensive overview of the project's goals, the structure of the Consortium, and key findings. In cases where more detailed presentations

were needed, posters were utilized to visually communicate the project's objectives and results, further enhancing outreach efforts.

Table 4. MAPWORMS events M1-M30.

Name	Date	Location	Type	Status	Partner	Contribution (organize/participate)	Size audience	Web site	Comments
DNA-Nanotechnology	12-14 May 2022	Germany	Conf	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: Stimuli-Responsive DNA-based hydrogels And Their Applications	80	Link	
Scuola di Orientamento Universitario – 2022 at SSSA	23 June 2022	Pisa (Italy)	Presentation	Presentation for young students	SSSA		>50	Link	
Festival del pensare	24 July 2022	Montescudaio, Italy	Festival	Participated as invited speaker	SSSA	Workshop "Il mio amico robot"	>200	Link	Festival for general public
Prof alla Torre!	04 August 2022	Porto Cesareo, Italy	Festival	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the MAPWORMS project through the conference "Vermi marini robot"	>50	Link	"Prof. alla Torre!" is the annual dissemination festival organised by the Marine Biology Museum of the University of Salento, aimed at introducing the marine biological research carried out at the University of Salento to the general public.
81 st Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	20-23 September 2022	Trieste, Italy	Conference	Participated	CoNISMa	Participated with the poster "Marine annelids as models for innovative robots"	>200	Link	
MINERVA Center for Biohybrid Materials School	6-11 November 2022	Israel	MINERVA School conference	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: Stimuli-Responsive Hydrogels for Nanomedicine, Self-Healing and Mechanical Applications	90		
G-quadruplex Webinar	19 January 2023	Virtual	Webinar	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: G-Quadruplex Responsive Hydrogels and Interphases, and Their Applications	200		
European Robotics Forum (ERF 2023)	14 – 16 March 2023	Odense, Denmark	Forum	Participated with poster	SSSA	Poster "Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS: the MAPWORMS Project"	>1000	Link	
International Ocean Data Conference - II (IODC-II)	20-21 March 2023	Paris, France	Conference	Participated	HCMR	Participate though the poster titled "Scientific community needs: FAIR and credible data repositories. The case of MedOBIS Repository and MAPWORMS Project"	>300	Link	International Ocean Data Conference - II (IODC-II)
6th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2023)	3-7 April 2023	Singapore	Conference	Participated	SSSA	Participated with poster titled "Mechanics of tubular meshes made of helical fibers and application to modeling McKibben artificial muscles"	>2000	Link	
2023 IEEE International Conference on	29 May – 2 June 2023	London (UK)	Conf	Participated	SSSA	Invited speaker at "Soft Robotics: Fusing function with structure" workshop	>500	Link	

Robotics and Automation (ICRA)										
Prof alla Torre!	01 July – 10 August 2023	Porto Cesareo	Festival	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the results of the first year of the MAPWORMS project	>50	Link	Dissemination festival	
I mercoledì della biologia marina	05 July – 03 August 2023	San Foca (Italy)	Festival	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the MAPWORMS project	>50	Link	Dissemination festival	
Living Machines 2023	10-13 July 2023	Genoa (Italy)	Conf	Participated	SSSA	Organizer of “worm-inspired machines” workshop	>1000	Link		
Invited Lecture	08 August 2023	East China University for Science and Technology	Presentation	Participated	HUJI	Invited Lecture: Dynamic hydrogel and Cryogel Materials and Their Applications	200			
14 th National Conference on Biodiversity/1 st International Conference on Mediterranean Biodiversity	13-15 September 2023	Lecce (Italy)	Conf	Participated	CoNISMa	Participated with the poster “Biodiversity patterns in marine annelids associated to intertidal coralline algae along the Salento Peninsula”	>150	Link		
82nd Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	19-22 September 2023	Palermo (Italy)	Conf	Participated	CoNISMa	Participated with the poster “Towards a new standard for marine annelid checklists: the Salento Peninsula as a case study”	>200	Link		
Lecce Fantafest	25-27 September 2023	Lecce (Italy)	Festival	Participated	CoNISMa	Participated to a round table on innovative technologies	>100	Link	Cineforum on science fiction movies with a round table of academic experts	
2 nd Congress Online on Marine Evolution	14-17 November 2023	Online event	Conf	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of some taxonomic results obtained in the context of the MAPWORMS project	>70	Link		
Innodays 2023	24-26 November 2023	Crete (Greece)	Exhibition	Participated	HCMR	Micro-CT scans were presented through a touchscreen monitor	>5000	Link	On the Mediterranean Agri-Food Competence Centre (MACC) stand, A touchscreen monitor was installed and the MAPWORMS micro-CT scans were displayed and the visitors could interactively manipulate them	
European Robotics Forum	13-15 March 2024	Rimini (Italy)	Forum	Participated	SSSA, ACMIT	Organizer of “Translational challenges of soft robotics in medical applications” workshop	>300	Link		
7th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2024)	14 April 2024	San Diego (USA)	Conference	Participated	SSSA	Presentation of the MAPWORMS project to the audience	>2000	Link		
The 18 th International Symposium on Macrocyclic and Supramolecular Chemistry	06-10 May 2024	Hangzhou China	Conf.	Participated	HUJI	Plenary lecture: Stimuli-Responsive Supramolecular Oligonucleotide Systems: From Functional Materials to Protocells	400	Link		

Pisa Robotics Festival 2024	26 May 2024	Pisa, Italy	Workshop	Participated with poster and a talk.	SSSA	Co-organizer of Workshop titled "Medical Robotics Workshop"	>50	Link	
5th International Congress on Applied Ichthyology, Oceanography, and Aquatic Environment (HydroMediT 2024)	30 May-2 June 2024	Mytilene (Greece)	Conference	Participated with presentation	HCMR	Presentation titled "Applying fair principles to micro-CT data, the case of MAPWORMS project"	>300	Link	
Oceanitalians	26 June 2024	Online event	Roundtable	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation the MAPWORMS project to the audience of the Oceanitalian facebook page	>100	Link	Dissemination online event also posted on the Youtube page of Oceanitalians
The Hamlyn Symposium on Medical Robotics	25 June 2024	London (UK)	Conference	Participated	SSSA	Presentation the MAPWORMS project to the audience	>500	Link	
The 11 th International Translational Conference on DNA-Nanotechnology	06-08 July 2024	Chengdu China	Conf.	Participated	HUJI	Plenary Lecture: Stimuli-Responsive Materials and Their Applications	200		
Invited Lecture	10 July 2024	Wuhan University, China	Presentation	Participated	HUJI	Invited Lecture: Dynamic Stimuli-Responsive Nanostructures, Materials, and Circuitries and Their Applications	150		
Award Lecture	04 Sept. 2024	San Sebastian, Spain	Presentation	Participated	HUJI	Invited Award Lecture: Dynamic Nucleic Acid Nanostructures and Systems: From fundamental Concepts to Applications	100		
83rd Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	11-14 September 2024	Pisa (Italy)	Conf	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the results of the first two years of the MAPWORMS project	>250	Link	
57 th European Marine Biology Symposium	16-20 September 2024	Naples (Italy)	Conf	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the results of the first two years of the MAPWORMS project	>250	Link	
Bright Night 2024	27 September 2024	Pisa, Italy	Exhibition	Participated	SSSA	Presentation of the MAPWORMS project to the general public	>250	Link	

Figure 7. (Top) People attending the presentation of the MAPWORMS project at the “Prof alla Torre” festival. (Bottom) People from SSSA presenting the MAPWORMS project at the Pisa Robotics Festival.

4. VIRTUAL GALLERIES OF THE VOUCHER SPECIMENS COLLECTION

Several annelid specimens belonging to Annelida including Sipuncula are being scanned through micro-CT. These micro-CT scans will be uploaded to the MAPWORMS open virtual collection (Figure 8) of the MicroCTvlab online repository (MicroCTvlab @ <https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>) for any potential user (including academics, scientists, students, artists and animators and everyone who is interested in microCT data).

Figure 8. The MAPWORMS specimen collection of the microCT scans

The MicroCTvlab will host annotated data and 3D models of the scanned annelids. This Voucher Specimens Collection will be uploaded in the Micro-CTvlab and a mobile application which will present virtual galleries of 3D micro-CT datasets of the annelid specimens and online tools for their manipulation and exploration (details will be reported in D1.10 – “Report on Virtual galleries of the Voucher Specimens Collection” due at month 48).

Figure 9 shows an example of an annelid micro-CT scan uploaded in the MAPWORMS collection. This relative microCT scan can be found in <https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/node/89>. Details about the functionalities of this virtual lab can be found in Keklikoglou et al. (2016).¹

Figure 9. Example of an annelid micro-CT scan uploaded in the MAPWORMS collection.

¹ Keklikoglou K, Faulwetter S, Chatziniolaou E, Michalakis N, Filiopoulou I, Minadakis N, Panteri E, Perantinos G, Gougousis A, Arvanitidis C (2016) Micro-CT : A web based virtual gallery of biological specimens using X-ray microtomography (micro-CT). Biodiversity Data Journal 4: e8740. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.4.e8740>

5. EXHIBITIONS

Annelida specimens collected in the framework of MAPWORMS will be permanently exposed in the Museum of Marine Biology of the University of Salento (ca. 10.000-13.000 visitors/year + online tours available) and multimedia panels will be used to describe annelid evolution, biology, ecology and to explain their potential as models for robotic applications profiting from MAPWORMS's results. At present, the Museum is undergoing a thorough renovation, which will end around November 2024. In the context of the reopening, a permanent exhibition on taxonomic and functional diversity of marine annelids, and their contribution to biomimetics using the material gathered during the MAPWORMS project will be established. Results of the project MAPWORMS were presented to the general public in the context of the dissemination festival “Prof alla Torre” organized by the Museum itself.

Dissemination material with the MAPWORMS results can be also exposed in the [CretAquarium](#) which is located in Crete Island (Greece).

Additionally, MAPWORMS micro-CT scans were presented at the [INNODAYS](#) innovation exhibition during 24-26 November 2023, organized by the Region of Crete (Figure 10). On the [Mediterranean Agri-Food Competence Centre \(MACC\)](#) stand, the Educational Unit of HCMR and the Cretaquarium aimed to inform children interactively about marine science issues based on the principle “Because Research, Knowledge and Innovation start with children...”.

In this framework, using the [Drishti Prayog](#) software, MAPWORMS micro-CT scans were displayed in a touch screen monitor and children had the ability to explore and interactively manipulate the 3D worms (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Innodays exhibition and the micro-CT scans displayed in the touchscreen monitor.

The project results were showcased at the 2023 and 2024 editions of the [Bright Night](#) - The European Researchers' Night in Pisa. This is a Europe-wide public event that disseminates science results and their impact on citizens' daily lives in a fun and inspiring way. In Pisa, many activities have been organized: mini-lectures, workshops, experiments, walks, demonstrations, and shows. Additionally, the project results were shown at both the 2023 and 2024 editions of the [Pisa Robotics Festival](#) (Figure 7 bottom). At both events, researchers involved in the project engaged with people of all ages and backgrounds, explaining the innovations behind soft robots inspired by biological species and able to adapt to various environments. These events allowed for valuable opportunities to demonstrate the project prototypes, explain their working mechanisms, and give attendees a hands-on understanding of the utilized materials and properties.

6. WORKSHOPS

Three workshops were organized within the project.

A workshop titled “Worm-Inspired Machines” ([webpage](#)) was organized in collaboration between SSSA and CoNISMa on July 10, 2023, as part of the Living Machines 2023 conference in Genoa, Italy. The event focused on the intersection of soft robotics and biology, drawing inspiration from the adaptability and movement of worms to create innovative robotic systems. Discussions covered worm-inspired technologies, biomechanics, and the challenges of translating biological principles into functional robots, while showcasing project results. Notable speakers from Stanford University, UC Santa Barbara, Case Western Reserve University, and the University of Southern Denmark provided valuable insights into the future of bioinspired robotics.

Another workshop titled “Translational Challenges of Soft Robotics in Medical Applications” ([webpage](#)) was organized in collaboration between SSSA and ACMIT on March 18, 2024 at the European Robotics Forum (ERF) 2024 in Rimini, Italy (Figure 11). The workshop explored innovative approaches in soft robotics and addressed the obstacles impeding the translation of these technologies into the market. Speakers from several well-known organizations like Italian Institute of Technology (Genova, Italy), Foundation of Cardiac Surgery (Zabrze, Poland), Artimus Robotics (Boulder, USA), Omnigrasp (Bari, Italy), and Politecnico di Milano (Milan, Italy) participated in the discussions and offered valuable perspectives on the future of soft robotics.

Additionally, a workshop titled “Fluid-driven soft actuators: challenges and opportunities” ([webpage](#)) was organized in collaboration between SSSA and Boston University on April 14, 2024 at the 7th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft) 2024 in San Diego, CA, USA (Figure 11). Throughout the workshop, open and comprehensive discussions addressed recent advancements and key challenges in soft fluid-driven actuators, bringing together internationally renowned experts from Cornell University, Sungkyunkwan University, the University of Illinois, the University of California, the University of Oxford, Rice University,

and the University of Bristol. In this context, numerous innovative solutions were presented for integrating morphological information within fluid-driven soft structures, enabling novel shape-morphing and fluid-control strategies. These insights suggest new approaches for developing soft robots that replicate fluidic mechanisms inspired by the hydrostatic skeletons of worms.

Figure 11. (Top) SSSA and CoNISMa from the MAPWORMS consortium organized the workshop “Worm-Inspired Machines” at Living Machines 2023. Organizers of the Workshop along with invited speakers (left) and Prof. Luigi Musco (CoNISMa) with Dr. Linda Paternò and Dr Jacopo Quaglierini (SSSA) introducing the workshop (right). (Center) ACMIT and SSSA from the MAPWORMS consortium organized the workshop “Translational Challenges of Soft Robotics in Medical Applications” at ERF 2024. Organizers of the Workshop along with some of the speakers (left) and Prof. Arianna Menciassi (SSSA) presenting worm-inspired machines (right). (Bottom) SSSA from the MAPWORMS consortium in collaboration with the Boston University organized the workshop “Fluid-driven soft actuators: challenges and opportunities” at RoboSoft 2024. Organizers of the Workshop (left) and Dr. Linda Paternò (SSSA) introducing the workshop (right).

7. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable outlines the dissemination and communication efforts undertaken during the 30-month MAPWORMS project, detailing the use of digital tools, publications, events, and outreach activities. These efforts included conference participation, updates on the MAPWORMS website, and targeted actions on social media platforms like LinkedIn and Facebook. Key performance indicators (KPIs) were used to track progress. Two major workshops were organized: one at Living Machines 2023 on worm-inspired machines, and another at the European Robotics Forum 2024 focused on soft robotics' translational challenges.

The consortium published five papers and submitted a sixth, all to high-impact journals. Despite falling short of the 30,000-visit target, the website attracted 17,185 visits, while LinkedIn emerged as the most effective social media platform with 659 followers, followed by 209 on Facebook.

This document is a living resource that will be updated in the third reporting period (M48) to reflect ongoing progress in dissemination and communication strategies.